

OBPDC 2024

2-4 October 2024

Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain

Biography Presenter

Session Name	Compression Algorithms
Day of the presentation	I'm not sure
Paper / Presentation Title	Predicting SAR Coherent Change Detection Error from Quantization Design

Name Presenter	Chris McGuinness
Nationality Presenter	USA
Affiliation Presenter and Location (City, Country)	Georgia Tech Research Institute Atlanta, USA
Present Position	Senior Research Engineer
Name of other entities involved in the paper	
Experience related to the presentation (Max 150 words)	Dr. McGuinness is the sustainment and transition lead for the United States Air Force data compression research and development program named RDUCE. His primary work for the past 10 years has been assessing compression algorithms to communicate data compression distortion in terms of mission impact for ISR system owners. This work spans EO, FMV, HSI, and SAR modalities.